

REVIVING RESILIENCE FROM THE TENTS - GAZA (2024)

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ABSTRACT

The ongoing humanitarian crisis in Gaza has resulted in unprecedented levels of physical and psychological suffering among its residents, with families experiencing repeated and forced displacement amid violence and destruction. This paper explores the profound challenges faced by Gazans, detailing their struggles for survival while emphasising their remarkable resilience.

Through a mixed methodology that includes life diaries and qualitative interviews conducted by the field researchers actively engaged with displaced communities, the study highlights the lived experiences of families enduring multiple displacements, often under threat of violence and deprivation of basic human needs. The literature review situates the Gaza experience within the broader context of displacement studies, revealing key themes such as community dynamics, psychological impacts, and the role of cultural identity in fostering resilience.

Findings demonstrate that despite the dire conditions of makeshift camps, Gazans exhibit incredible resourcefulness and solidarity, adapting to their harsh realities through communal support systems and cultural preservation. The study underscores the significance of social networks in mitigating trauma, suggesting that resilience is not merely an individual trait but a collective endeavour. While this paper raises awareness of Gaza's humanitarian needs, it also offers insights into the resilience strategies employed by its displaced populations.

Keywords: Resilience, Displacement, Gaza, Humanitarian Crisis, Psychological Impact, Community Support, Cultural Identity, Social Networks Life Diaries, Collective Memory.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The people of Gaza continue to endure immense physical and psychological suffering. Homes have been destroyed, factories and businesses obliterated, and loved ones have been killed, displaced, injured, or lost. Every family in Gaza has experienced some form of loss or deprivation—whether in terms of loved ones, wealth, or property. According to statistics, approximately 10% of Gaza’s population is either martyred, missing, or injured, with the entire population experiencing repeated displacement, even after a full year of the genocidal war against Gaza. Buheji (2024c)

In this forced displacement, the people of Gaza have been left with no option but to live in makeshift camps, enduring life in tents with no access to basic human needs—adequate shelter, security, food, water, clothing, hygiene, health, privacy, or education.

The residents of Gaza have endured repeated expulsion and displacement under fire, shelling, and death. During interviews conducted by the researchers—who frequently visit the displacement camps and spend hours speaking with the displaced about their conditions and circumstances—many families reported being displaced more than ten times, moving from one place to another, either within or between governorates. Al-Muhannadi and Buheji (2024a)

Despite the harshness of life, the people of Gaza have shown patience and adapted to their new reality, clinging to the hope of returning to what remains of their homes, even if it is just to the ruins and memories. People of all ages, young and old, male and female, have strived to find creative solutions to the challenges of their bitter reality. Migdad and Buheji (2024b)

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Gazan and History of Consistent Displacement

In recent decades, Gaza has faced a series of displacements due to ongoing conflict, political instability, and humanitarian crises. This literature review examines existing scholarship on resilience in the context of displacement, with a particular focus on the Palestinian experience in Gaza. It highlights key themes in the literature, including definitions of resilience, community dynamics, psychological impacts, and the role of culture and identity in fostering resilience. Al-Muhannadi and Buheji (2024b)

2.2. Community Dynamics and Social Support Resilience

Resilience is frequently discussed in the context of displacement, yet definitions vary significantly across disciplines. While some researchers describe resilience as the ability to bounce back from adversity, others emphasise the adaptive processes that enable individuals and communities to thrive despite challenges. In the context of Gaza, resilience is often linked to both individual and collective coping strategies that emerge in response to sustained hardships. Buheji (2024b)

The role of social networks in building resilience among displaced populations has been extensively documented. Studies show that strong community ties can mitigate the impacts of trauma and displacement by providing emotional and practical support. In Gaza, community organisations and grassroots initiatives have emerged as critical resources for fostering resilience, facilitating social cohesion, and addressing the needs of displaced individuals. Buheji and Hasan (2024b)

2.3. Psychological Impacts of Displacement

Displacement is associated with various psychological challenges, including PTSD, anxiety, and depression. However, research indicates that resilience can counteract these negative effects. For instance, studies have shown that maintaining a sense of hope and purpose can significantly enhance mental health outcomes for those affected by displacement. Within Gaza, narratives of resilience often highlight the importance of hope and perseverance, suggesting that psychological resilience can be cultivated even amid adversity. Migdad and Buheji (2024b)

2.4. Cultural Identity and Resilience

Cultural identity plays a pivotal role in resilience among displaced populations. Literature emphasises that cultural practices, traditions, and community narratives contribute to a sense of belonging and purpose. In Gaza, efforts to uphold Palestinian culture—through art, literature, and community events—serve not only to preserve identity but also to strengthen resilience by fostering solidarity and collective memory.

Addressing the needs of displaced communities in Gaza requires a nuanced understanding of resilience that encompasses social, psychological, and cultural dimensions. This means more frameworks need to be developed to enhance community support systems, promote mental health initiatives, and safeguard the cultural heritage of those living in the displacement. Future research should explore innovative approaches to resilience-building that engage Gaza's local communities in the recovery process.

3. METHODOLOGY

Two of the research team members have created a life diary that reflects on the displacement challenges, suffering, and resilience of the displaced Palestinian community in Gaza. The detailed documentation is meant to share the people's experiences in a daily diary structure. The researchers recorded the date and specific location to provide context. The diary briefly explains the displacement situation, including historical and political factors that contribute to the current state of the Palestinian community. Migdad and Buheji (2024a)

The conditions of temporary shelters or refugee camps are intentionally part of the methodology used to write the case study, supported by the pictures. The researchers describe in detail the challenges and resilience in dealing with shortages of food, water, and medical care and how these affect Gazans' daily lives.

The note-taking methodology also includes details of the threats of the breakdown of community ties and their impact on social structures due to the intensity of displacement conditions. In some instances, the researchers even share stories of individuals and families, highlighting traumatic experiences that illustrate displacement's emotional and psychological toll. They note instances of violence or loss that affect families.

The observations collected by the two field researchers from Gaza reflect how the displaced communities support one another, including sharing resources and information. The researchers also documented the efforts taken by the Gazan families to maintain cultural practices, traditions, and identity even in displacement. The notes highlight actions taken by community members or organisations to challenge their circumstances and promote their rights.

4. CASE STUDY

4.1 The Repeated Displacement and Its Hardships

As previously mentioned, hundreds of thousands of families in Gaza have been displaced nearly ten times. Each displacement brings new suffering, stories of loss, and casualties. The process of displacement is physically and psychologically devastating, even if it occurs only once. Imagine when it happens over ten times, each time following intense shelling and the threat of losing children, families, homes, and livelihoods. Buheji and Buheji (2024)

During an interview with a displaced family, they explained that they moved their remaining belongings in an expensive rented vehicle after their shelter was bombed for the eighth time, and they were forced to flee again for the ninth time. Two of their children were killed in the random and unjust bombardment. A family member said, "Two of our family (referring to the martyrs) lived, but we are dying. We are living in conditions worse than death. We have nowhere to go, no shelter, no means of living, and nothing to pay for transportation. Only God knows our plight, and we don't know how to continue living under these unbearable conditions."

Each instance of displacement represents a slow form of death, intensifying the suffering. The Israeli military seems aware of this, deliberately issuing evacuation orders to further the people's misery, intending to coerce them into abandoning their homeland, paving the way for the establishment of "Greater Israel," stretching from the river to the sea. But God is our refuge, and upon Him we rely.

4.2 A New Displacement with No Shelter

In mid-August, the Israeli military issued large-scale evacuation orders from Al-Bureij, Al-Maghazi, and areas east of Al-Nuseirat and Deir Al-Balah, triggering heavy shelling and massacres that forced people to flee from the threatened areas. But where could they go? No land remains free of tents, and the so-called safe regions barely cover 10% of Gaza's already limited space.

As the researchers walked through these conditions, he witnessed a startling sight: displaced people setting up their tents on the Zawaida garbage dump, finding space for their shelters amidst piles of waste, amid dangerous disease and pollution risks. The image below shows tents beside garbage mounds, with more tents on the other side of the road, also surrounded by trash. The displaced family had no choice—there was nowhere else to go. Even on the beach, the tents are battered by waves, which will likely drive thousands of tents inland during winter, as the sea's reach extends 20 to 30 meters. These tents, made of flimsy fabric, cannot withstand winter winds, rain, or flooding. People cannot survive under these conditions if the war continues through the winter, no matter how much they try to endure. The torn and worn-out tents will not protect against the cold, wind, or rain. Migdad and Buheji (2024c)

Figure (1) Tents amid landfill, in middle Gaza/ taken by the researchers

In an interview with a displaced man living at the Zawaida garbage dump, a father of seven, he said, "I had no choice but to place the tent in the dump, fully aware of the risks to my family. We arrived here, exhausted, and sat amidst death." He then added, "We are fleeing from death to death."

4.3 A Feel of Life Inside the Tent of the Displaced

Let us step into a tent to see a displaced Gazan family from the inside, the Palestinian family that cherishes life like any other. In a 4-meter by 3-meter tent, a family of five lives. Inside the tent, there is a kitchen, a bathroom, and a washing barrel. Next to the tent, the family grows basil, as they love the scent of nature and pleasant aromas, much like their love for life, as the mother of the family expressed in an interview.

Attached are photos of the tent's garden from both inside and outside, along with images of gardens belonging to other tents. Additionally, there are photos of the gardens surrounding other tents, where most tents have a small garden as well.

Figure (2) Gardening Despite Consistent Displacement

Inside the tent, the family operates by distributing tasks between each member knowing their role. When the call for "sweet water, sweet water" (drinkable water) is heard, hundreds of children rush to grab water containers and start lining up, waiting for hours, sometimes two or three, to fill their containers. The researchers captured the moment when the water truck arrived, showing the people lined up to fill their containers, (see picture below). The girls know their duties in kneading dough, washing dishes, and cleaning, while the boys take the dough to bake in the communal clay oven fueled by firewood. The older youths and adults typically help the father by securing a livelihood, either through work and earning money or by finding places to redeem coupons for food. They feel accomplished when they manage to secure enough food for the family to last for more than a day. Hassoun et al. (2024)

This is how Palestinians from Gaza live, and this is their love for life and beauty. This tent, located in the displacement camp in al-Mawasi Khan Younis, is one of approximately 70 tents where we document the lives of the displaced.

As I walked between the tents, I noticed that most of them had a small garden of basil, flowers, and shrubs. Even in displacement and tents, we plant, even if it is for the sake of beauty, scent, and pleasure. The researchers observed children tending to these gardens, watering the plants with the precious water they worked hard to obtain, despite the difficulties. Migdad et al. (2024a)

Figure (3) Illustration of Small Gardening near Each Tent in the Displacement Camp

As a show of collaborative resilience, around the tents, you might usually see a shared 1000-litre water tank, as shown in the picture. The tank, located beneath the worn-out tent after four months of use, is filled by the combined efforts of the families sharing it to ensure a continuous water supply for everyone. Additionally, each family has its own smaller water tank.

Figure (4) The Shared Water Tank between the Tents

There is a communal bathroom and toilet, which adds to the hardship. Unfortunately, the bathroom situation is a significant challenge for living in tents. Even bathing becomes a struggle due to the water shortage and the large number of people sharing the facilities, which leads to the spread of contagious skin diseases. Recently, a polio outbreak has occurred among children, prompting the World Health Organization (WHO) to bring hundreds of thousands of vaccines to Gaza. Despite the dire need for these vaccines among displaced children, the Israeli government has delayed granting a humanitarian ceasefire for a week to allow medical teams to administer the vaccines. Although the vaccines have reached Gaza's health warehouses, their distribution has been hindered. In the end, the Israeli government agreed to halt military operations in the vaccination areas for a limited number of hours.

4.4. Preparing Food in the Tent

Many families use their skills and hobbies to prepare food from their limited supplies, bringing a sense of life into the tent. They make mild pudding when they have access to milk and bake cakes and Palestinian desserts (Nammoura) with the flour and sugar available to them. They also prepare Pickled eggplants (Makdous) whenever they can find the ingredients.

The photo below shows makdous made in tents of displaced families. Makdous is made from small, boiled eggplants stuffed with garlic, red pepper and walnuts, then submerged into olive oil. It is considered a luxury dish, expensive and rarely available unless the necessary ingredients can be found. Additionally, families make Turkish delights (Halquom) for personal use and sale to others in the tent camps. The researchers interviewed a family that started making halquom, date cookies (ma'amol) and semolina cookies (ghraybeh) for home consumption. Over time, as demand increased, they expanded production for sale. Their products became popular, providing the family a modest income to help cover living costs under challenging circumstances. In an interview with a family from the Nuseirat area who produced halquom, cakes and ghraybeh, the mother shared that she initially made these items for her family. As demand grew, they began producing in larger quantities for sale. When their business gained a strong market presence and generated reasonable profits, the whole family, without exception, became involved in the business.

Figure (5) Type of Sweets Done Despite Limited Sources and Continuous Displacement

4.5 Life of Children in Displacement Camps

Children are seen playing and having fun, seemingly unaware of the war around them. They laugh as if there is no genocide. But when the bombings begin, each child clings to their mother or father, terrified of the noise. The devastation is unimaginable when a missile hits a tent nearby. Bodies are torn apart, blood flows, and any survivor is left injured, burned and blackened by debris and stained with their blood. One child, while the researchers were walking through the camp, he asked, “Baba, when will the war end? We want to live. I don’t want to die. Baba, why us? For how long?” The father and mother have no answer. No one has an answer, not even the highest-ranking Palestinian or Israeli politician. This is not a war; it is a genocide. There are no equal military forces; the alliances are grossly imbalanced. One side is supplied by the world with all kinds of weapons, from the US, UK, NATO and even some Arab countries, receiving hundreds of thousands of tons of weapons. The other side is besieged, deprived, without supplies or alliances, receiving only hundreds of tons of canned peas and beans, now selling 50 shekels per can (1 USD equals 3.7 NIS). These cans are no longer sold, but are thrown away in garbage dumps for the vast numbers they are sent to Gaza, exceeding the needs of the people and sometimes the passing of the expiry date. People who sell these cans would sell it very cheap (5-10 cans for 10 NIS), and they would leave the rest on the floor if they decide to leave.

Returning to the tent, you can’t imagine the unbearable heat. The temperature inside the tent exceeds 45 degrees Celsius. There is no electricity or cooling, fans, air conditioning, or windows. People have no place to sit from 8 am to 6 pm. As a result, men, women, and children flee the tents, searching for any wall or shadow to escape the heat and feel relief. After four months of displacement from Rafah to al-Mawasi Khan Younis, the patched-up tents are now worn out, no longer offering protection from the summer heat or the scorching sun, Migdad et al. (2024b). As winter approaches, the hope is that the genocide will end before the cold sets in. But, God forbid, if the war continues into winter, the displaced will be flooded, either from direct rain, or from the torrents running under their tents. The tattered tents can’t protect their inhabitants from the heat and will not shield them from the rain, cold or wind. The displaced are in great distress, fearing what has to come, yet holding onto hope that the war will soon end.

Those displaced to the coast, just meters away from the waves, are also at risk. When the sea surges during winter, the thousands of tents near the shore will be swept away by the relentless waves.

The UNRWA communications officer confirmed that the situation in Gaza is catastrophic, with safe zones becoming more overcrowded and the risk of disease outbreaks increasing. There is no safe place in Gaza, and the humanitarian response has become limited due to repeated evacuation orders. This highlights the difficulty of life in the displacement camps, which have become breeding grounds for epidemics, diseases, and death spreading throughout the region.

4.6 A Moment of Joy for the Displaced Children

One day, the lead researchers received money from kind relatives abroad to help the afflicted and displaced people of Gaza. He decided to bring some joy to the children by purchasing tracksuits for them. The children in the al-Mawasi Khan Younis displacement camp who lacked shoes and proper clothing, lined up as shown in the picture below. About 100 children received a tracksuit. The joy on each child's face upon receiving the tracksuit was evident. Phusavat and Buheji (2024)

The researchers saw their smiles and watched them return to their mothers, feeling like they had achieved something remarkable. Why such joy? Because they have no other new clothes, and their parents can't afford to buy them. Even if some parents had the money, no suitable garments were available in the market. The siege had wiped out any stock of clothing or other goods. If not for a merchant with an old stockpile, we wouldn't have been able to provide the tracksuits. The distribution was completed, and the happiness extended to the parents as well, when seeing their children's joys. See the pictures below.

Figure (6) Illustrates the joy Among Children While Receiving New Cloth

The children and parents thanked us and thanked those who donated to us, and asked us with hope and desperation to please continue providing assistance. The team asked them what they wanted. They said “a dress for women or a jalabiya, because our clothes are worn out, and we do not have the money to buy anything, and we do not find anything in the markets to buy.

Our hope is great in God, then in you and in the good people who communicate with you. Praise be to God, and on Him we rely and to Him we complain, and we ask God for safety.”

4.7 A Night of Fear, Terror, and Uncertainty

On the night of August 25th, 2024, around 11 PM, several rockets were launched from the south. Half an hour later, we learned from the news that they had landed in Tel Aviv. On the same day, Hezbollah targeted a ship and multiple military sites in the occupying state.

At the same time, the displaced people of Gaza anxiously awaited the results of ongoing negotiations, hoping they would lead to a ceasefire and an end to the killing and genocide of innocent, unarmed civilians. Yet, the relentless Israeli bombardment, which had never truly stopped, escalated into sheer madness. Optimism among Gazans began to fade, replaced by fear and growing pessimism over the continuation of the massacres.

It was now 1 AM, and the researcher, visiting family in al-Mawasi Khan Younis, found it impossible to sleep or endure the heat inside the tent. He decided to sleep outside in an open space between the tents, an area where they prayed during the day, and where the camp residents gathered for evening chats, children’s games, and Quran lessons.

He tried to sleep but couldn’t, so he started writing, documenting what was happening, what he felt, and what the people around him were experiencing. It was a night filled with terror, fear, and anticipation. Fear of the bombs and the dismemberment they could cause, fear of an unexpected invasion by the occupying forces, and the unsettling feeling of being in a strange, unfamiliar place. There was also a fear of thieves who, sadly, prowled the camps at night. That night, the fear was overwhelming. The sound of the bombardment was terrifying, harsh, and close. The rustling wind gave the strange impression that someone was moving in the darkness. The movement of a cat or a dog was enough to make one suspect it was a thief.

Unable to sleep, the researcher began reciting the Quran: Al-Fatiha, Ayat al-Kursi, and the protective Surahs. He prayed for the safety of the displaced, wherever they were. The researcher entrusted himself, his family, his wealth, and his home to God, continuing to write these reflections as he tossed and turned, hoping for sleep, for safety, and that the night would pass peacefully...

The researcher attempted to stop writing and sleep, but sleep eluded him. The sky was filled with drones, resembling stars but more like black crows. The buzzing of drones was relentless, accompanied by bombardments at short intervals. No one knew where the bombs were falling, what was destroyed, who had been killed, or what new massacre had been committed, until the news came from journalists risking their lives to report the truth. All we could say was, "God is sufficient for us, and He is the best disposer of affairs," cursing those who wronged and abandoned us.

Sleep still hadn’t come to the researcher. By 2 AM, he thought he heard someone speaking. Startled, he jumped up, calling out, “Who’s there? Who’s there?” But no one answered, and no one in the camp stirred. The researcher took a walk between the tents but found nothing alarming, so he returned to his spot between the tents and remained awake until dawn, waiting for the Fajr-dawn prayer. Mosquitoes attacked him, his hands and legs covered in intense itching, the pain unbearable. With no solution but patience, he remembered his grandmother’s advice about the healing properties of olive oil. He found some and applied it to his legs, and by God’s grace, the itching subsided. Buheji (2024a)

The call to prayer for Fajr was heard. After praying, one of the researchers returned to his spot, not knowing if he would finally be able to sleep. Exhausted, he slept for two hours before the scorching sun attacked at 7 AM, along with the shouts of children who gathered in the same area every morning to play and socialise. There was no way to stop them, nor was it my right to, for they had no other place to play.

4.8 A Day in the Scorching Heat

While visiting family—siblings and a daughter—at a displacement camp in Khan Younis, the researcher had no choice but to spend the night there. Unable to sleep in the tent, he stayed outside in the open air next to the tent, in one of the shelters. He was filled with anxiety and remained awake until dawn.

We went out to buy some goods for trade, hoping to generate a small income to cover the costs of living. From 10 AM, the heat of hell surrounded us, and the temperature intensified. We couldn't find any cool shade for relief, and the heat was unbearable as the sun bore down on us. There was no transportation, forcing us to walk several kilometers. We bought some goods and returned to the camp. Migdad et al. (2024c)

After the exhaustion, fatigue, and lack of sleep the night before, the researcher had a short nap around noon. But it was nearly impossible despite his overwhelming drowsiness. He tossed and moved in heat and sweat, while the bedding was scorching hot. There was no cool place to find relief. He was on the edge of losing his patience, caught between the searing heat and the dozens of children playing nearby, laughing and shouting. He couldn't stop them, nor could he send them away. The heat was oppressive, the temperature nearing 40°C and rising to over 45°C inside the tent, with no alternative space available. Buheji (2024a)

The researcher endured and remained patient, having no other choice. His patience was running out when his brother arrived and invited him to join him in a rented room in a partially destroyed building, but it was cool and tolerable. The researcher had lunch there and stayed for a while, finally finding relief from the heat, and praise to God for His mercy.

Figure (7) Photo of the children playing between Tent:

4.9 Community Kitchens in the Life of the Camps

Community kitchens, or "takkayas," have become common sight around the displacement camps. A "takkaya" is a place where meals, typically hot soups like lentil, bean, or pea soup, are prepared and distributed. Occasionally, rice is also cooked, sometimes accompanied by meat or chicken, when available. The meals are handed out to those who come to receive food.

Crowds tend to gather in larger numbers at the takkayas that offer rice with meat or chicken, often leading to difficulties in managing lines and maintaining order, resulting in frequent issues among the people and the management. Some of the kitchens, particularly those distributing meat and chicken, have shifted from open distribution to a more organised system, where representatives from the tents collect food on behalf of the families they are responsible for, reducing chaos. Buheji and Hasan (2024a)

Many of these takkayas are run by families, funded primarily by family members, with additional support from relatives living outside of Palestine, particularly those who are financially well-off. These families manage the kitchens to serve the displaced residents of the camps. Other takkayas are operated by cooperative and Othmani organisations that were active even before the war. Some were established during the conflict through international organisations, such as the World Central Kitchen (WCK), which has become well-known for setting up dozens of both central and satellite kitchens across Gaza.

Figure (8) Photo of the Food Preparation in one of the Takkaya's in Gaza

4.10 The Challenging of Visiting Family Members in Other Camps

Given the dire economic and security conditions, movement and travel between displacement camps are extremely difficult and financially burdensome. As a result, such visits are minimized and made only when absolutely necessary. To visit family in another camp just six kilometres away, one needs at least four hours for the round trip, in addition to 40 shekels, which most people cannot afford. Therefore, visits are often done on foot or by bicycle for those who can manage.

These visits are typically brief, in accordance with the saying, "A visit is like a raid." There are no proper facilities for hosting guests, nor sufficient provisions to offer hospitality. Consequently, visits are rare, short, and usually serve purposes beyond just visiting, except for close family members.

It is notable that families were not able to evacuate together. In an interview with some displaced families, one man was asked about his siblings and other family members. He said, "When the evacuation order came, we hesitated, and then the random shelling began. We became separated, not knowing where each person went. Each of my brothers took his wife and children and fled in a different direction, so that even if they were bombed, not everyone would be killed, and someone from the family would survive to carry on."

Figure (9) One of the Field Researchers Visiting Cousins in Deir al-Balah displacement camp.

4.11 Electricity and Internet in the Life of Displacement Camps

The war has entered its twelfth month, and we are about to start the second year of this genocide against the people of Gaza. As we enter the new year, it is essential to note that we have had no electricity for a long time, severely impacting every aspect of life. The electricity network, power generation plants, and distribution facilities have been destroyed, making it impossible to access power.

Some private generators exist, but they do not supply electricity to the residents due to the exorbitant price of diesel and the limited production, which barely covers the generator owners' needs for daily living or business purposes, making electricity nearly unattainable.

In response, displaced people have resorted to basic solar panel setups. Those who own a panel use it to charge batteries for lighting and mobile phones. Some individuals have turned this into a small business, charging other people's phones for a modest fee.

As for the internet, the situation is similarly dire. Some households with internet access via the Palestinian telecommunications company before the war can still access it if they remain in their homes. However, these homes are few. Others, who had subscription-based internet packages, continue to access the service, though the connection is weak and frequently disrupted, barely sufficient for basic browsing on Facebook or WhatsApp and sending messages.

During the war, some companies began selling internet access cards, allowing displaced people to connect at certain times and locations. These cards work for 4 or 8 hours upon activation. However, these connections are slow and unreliable due to the high demand.

It is worth mentioning that at the time of this writing, the researchers are struggling to send this research to partners for review and collaboration. It could take up to a week or longer to send the document through the Internet for further input and publication.

4.11 Importance of Palestinian Women in the Displacement

Palestinian women in the displacement camps, especially in the al-Mawasi area of Khan Younis, are the backbone of the camp. They manage their homes, particularly as men are preoccupied with securing financial resources for survival. Women tend to their children, maintain their tents, and ensure everything is in order. Buheji et al. (2024)

These resilient women have endured the pain of displacement, loss, and uncertainty. They have lost sons, husbands, fathers, and mothers, yet they continue to persevere. Whether they are supporting their husbands or grieving their losses, these mothers remain steadfast, entrusting their hardships to God and seeking His reward. They do everything in their power to maintain stability for their families, despite the extreme challenges of camp life, hunger, and deprivation.

4.12 Escaping Camp Life to Exhibit Art in Dublin:

This is the story of Safa, a displaced woman who endured the hardships of camp life and repeated displacement. By the will of God, she managed to travel abroad during the war. Safa is an artist with dozens of paintings and the ability to create beautiful embroidered works representing Palestine, including symbols like the flag, the keffiyeh, the tent, hunger, poverty, and more. With the help of supporters in Dublin who sympathise with the people of Palestine, she participated in an important art exhibition where she displayed and sold all of her paintings.

Following the success of her first exhibition, Safa held a second, and she is now preparing for her third. Her exhibitions showcase Palestinian products and assert Palestinian identity through art, painting, embroidery, and the creative talent passed down through her family.

Figure (10) Palestinians in the Diaspora Supporting Gaza through Arts and Exhibition

5. CONCLUSION

This case study paper shows the resilience amidst displacement in Gaza and how it underscores the complex interplay between individual and community dynamics. By examining the multifaceted aspects of resilience, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of how displaced populations can navigate challenges and foster hope in the face of adversity. Continued research and targeted interventions are essential for supporting resilience and promoting sustainable recovery in Gaza.

In conclusion, the life of displacement in tents is an unimaginable experience for the people of Gaza—in terms of its duration, the extent of loss, the hardship of daily survival, and the ability to endure it all. The people of Gaza in these camps have suffered through every form of physical and psychological torment, facing a severe shortage of money, lives, and provisions, while holding on to the hope promised by God in the holy Quran: "And We will surely test you with some fear and hunger, and with paucity of wealth and lives and crops; and give glad tidings to those who patiently endure. And certainly, We shall test you with something of fear, hunger, loss of wealth, lives and fruits, but give glad tidings to As-Sabirin (the patient ones, etc.)." (Al-Baqarah 2:155)

Despite these overwhelming challenges, the displaced people of Gaza have demonstrated remarkable resilience in finding solutions to the immense difficulties faced by those living in the camps, amidst siege, hunger, and deprivation. They have tackled the many urgent tasks arising from this sudden and complex life.

The displaced Gazans have managed, at least partially, to address issues such as electricity, internet access, and securing water and food—though often at significant physical and emotional cost and sometimes at the expense of their health and dignity. Everyone—men, women, children, the sick, and the wounded—has contributed to finding ways to maintain a minimal standard of living, in the hope of escaping death and in the faith of a brighter future, God willing.

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